

Performance Modeling of Discharging Process in a Thermochemical Fluid System Using Machine Learning Approaches

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Abstract. Open absorption system is an energy efficient method for dehumidification/humidification. As the global demand for clean energy continues to rise, the significance of machine learning in forecasting energy systems will amplify. In this paper, we developed three machine learning algorithms to accurately forecast air output mixing ratio and temperature of a thermochemical fluid system and compare their performance. The variables used to forecast our responses are ambient air temperature (°C), inlet air mixing ratio (g/kg), the inlet desiccant temperature(°C), the air mass flow rate (kg/s) and desiccant mass flow rate (kg/s). The evaluation metrics shows Random Forest regressor greatly outperform multi-layer perceptron neural network, and is slightly better than Gradient boosting regressor. The Random Forest regressor stands out with a significant R^2 of 0.999 for predicting both air output mixing ratio and temperature, accompanied by MAPE values of 0.241 and 0.097, for air output mixing ratio and temperature prediction, respectively.

1. Introduction

With the rising costs of energy, the quest for energy-efficient methods for various applications becomes imperative (Rissman et al., 2020). An absorption TCF system or desiccant-based system is an efficient method for dehumidification/humidification (Buchholz et al., 2006). Also, a key benefit of absorption TCF systems lies in the direct conversion of latent heat into sensible heat. The heat released during the absorption process returns to the building, aiding in heating the air. Also, the TCF system provide a solution for challenge of seasonal storage process from summer to winter ensuring no losses (Buchholz et al., 2009). The absorption TCF system, employing liquid desiccants, aims to reduce energy consumption in various building tasks, including cooling, heating, humidity control, and water recovery (Buchholz et al., 2009). As absorption processes are driven by thermal energy, they present a viable substitute for conventional electricity-driven vapor compression refrigeration systems, leading to a reduction in electricity consumption (Amani et al., 2020). Therefore, a TCF system based on hygroscopic salt solutions (particularly those based on CaCl_2 , MgCl_2 and LiCl_2 salts) is an efficient method for dehumidifying processes and the recovery of latent heat (Geyer, 2009; Geyer et al., 2017). Numerous researchers have directed their attention toward novel sorption materials, specifically matrices infused with salt. Several distinct research have been conducted within this domain (Jarimi et al., 2018; Mehrabadi & Farid, 2018).

The TCF system involves processes complex to design and model, which involves advanced engineering knowledge to find a well-performing solution. There are mainly two approaches for modeling TCF systems: physic-based and data-driven modeling. Physics-based modeling of TCF systems (Chen et al., 2016; Delwati et al., 2019; Geyer et al., 2018) compared to machine learning models often involve making assumptions and simplifications to model such complex systems. If these assumptions do not accurately reflect the real-world conditions, the physics-based models' results are less reliable (Alaoui et al., 2023). Also, examining TCF systems using conventional physics-based models and laboratory investigations incurs substantial financial expenses(Çolak et al., 2022; Praditia et al., 2020). On the other hand, Machine Learning (ML)

models are cost effective and proved to be highly accurate in modeling complex nonlinear datasets (Milićević et al., 2023). Tasneem et al., (Tasneem et al., 2023) showed the effectiveness of ML models for predicting the dynamic behavior of reversible thermochemical energy storage system. In other research, the effectiveness of models based on neural networks on thermochemical energy storage's reaction prediction are explored (Çolak et al., 2022; Praditia et al., 2020). To the best of our knowledge, implementing ML models for predicting the open absorption TCF system is new and need to be explored to fulfill a gap related with implementing computational tools for forecasting open absorption TCF systems performance.

Machine learning modelling of open absorption TCF system using real data obtained through experimental study is the main objective of this research. This comprises developing monolithic black box machine learning models, and comparing their performance in predicting the open absorption TCF system performance and finding the best model to predict the performance of the system in terms of dehumidification.

2. Experimental dataset

The distributor bed, serving as the central component of the TCF (Thermo-Chemical Fluid) systems, is meticulously constructed with hexagonal compartments to optimize contact between water and air. Through a spiral-shaped arrangement of plastic and textile, the contact area is effectively facilitated. Utilizing a counterflow design, the system maximizes the interaction between air and desiccant, ensuring efficient dehumidification as the desiccant evenly permeates the bed. The resulting diluted solution is efficiently collected in a dedicated storage tank. Two tanks, capable of accommodating both concentrated and diluted solutions, are employed for storage purposes. To maintain the requisite liquid temperature for experimental conditions, a heat exchanger connected to a heat pump is employed. Additionally, two corrosion-resistant pumps are carefully selected to regulate desiccant flow within the system. A fan, positioned atop the absorber cabin, facilitates the upward movement of air from the lower section to the upper part. To comprehensively monitor heat transfer across the absorber bed, high-precision temperature sensors are strategically positioned at various locations. Capacitive relative humidity sensors are integrated to analyze inlet and outlet air characteristics, providing precise measurements for temperature and relative humidity. Furthermore, a differential pressure sensor is installed at the air outlet before the ventilator to assess air velocity, while a magnetic flow meter near the heat exchanger accurately measures desiccant flow rate.

To further enhance control and simulate varying temperature and humidity conditions, the TCF system has been relocated to a climatic chamber at the Institute for Solar Energy Research in Hamelin.

The desiccant solution is Magnesium Chloride with a concentration of 31%. The effects of various variables including ambient air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), inlet air mixing ratio (g/kg), the inlet desiccant temperature($^{\circ}\text{C}$), the air mass flow rate (kg/s) and desiccant mass flow rate (kg/s) on the system's efficiency are examined. Table 1 shows the data ranges and levels used for the experiments. Also, a schematic of the open absorption TCF system is depicted in Figure 1, showing all the components and sensors utilized in the experimental study. The gathered data enable the determination and prediction of moisture sorption offering valuable insights into the capabilities of data-driven machine learning models.

Table 1: Operating parameters and their ranges.

Variables	Inlet air relative humidity (%)	Inlet air temperature (°C)	Inlet desiccant temperature (°C)	Air flow rate (m ³ /h)	Desiccant flow rate (l/min)	Contact time (min)	Desiccant concentration (%)
levels	60-90	20-40	10-40	300-500	1.5-2.5	10	31

Figure 1: Schematic of the open absorption TCF systems.

Moisture absorption by the TCF system in different input mixing ratio is shown in Figure 2 demonstrating effectiveness of the system in water vapor absorption from air.

Figure 2: Humidity absorption by TCF system.

3. Methodology

This study focuses on the data-driven modeling of absorption-based TCF systems. The experimental investigation is done for an open absorption TCF system in a laboratory-scale in a climatic chamber. This paper emphasizes the role of machine learning models in predicting the output air mixing ratio (g/kg) and air output temperature (°C). The research decomposes the problem to a supervised learning scheme and applies Gradient Boosting Regressor (GBR), Random Forest Regressor (RFR), and Multi-Layer Perceptron neural network (MLP) to forecast the system's outputs, comparing their performance comprehensively. To predict the discharging air mixing ratio, four specific input parameters are defined: input air temperature (°C), input liquid temperature (°C), air mass flow rate (kg/s), and brine mass flow rate (kg/s). Additionally, for predicting output air temperature, four input parameters are taken into account: input air mixing ratio (g/kg), input liquid temperature (°C), air mass flow rate (kg/s), and brine mass flow rate (kg/s).

Prior to modeling, preprocessing the dataset is imperative. The experimental data, obtained directly from sensors operating continuously, required thorough cleaning, particularly regarding the state transitions of pumps and ventilators. Additionally, it was essential to account for the impact of variable changes until reaching a steady state during the experiments. Furthermore, challenges arose in stabilizing ambient humidity and temperature to achieve this steady state. Addressing these issues, as well as outliers, involved employing various methods such as filtering and applying moving averages to cleanse the data effectively.

To assess the model's performance, it's crucial to partition the data into separate training and testing sets. In this case, 70% of the dataset was designated for training, with the remaining portion allocated for testing. This split ensures a substantial amount of data for training the model while retaining a distinct subset for evaluating its performance.

3.1 Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network

Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) is a class of feedforward neural networks consisting of multiple layers of interconnected nodes, known as neurons. MLPs are characterized by their ability to flexibly learn complex nonlinear relationships from data. The MLP algorithms require careful tuning of its architecture, activation functions, and regularization techniques in order to achieve a good fit and prevent overfitting. Also, training time compared to the other two algorithms can be computationally expensive especially for deep structures (Marius-Constantin et al., 2009). The MLP model employs a feed-forward back propagation (FF-BP) multilayer perceptron (MLP) network. MLP neural networks, characterized by their layered architecture, are widely utilized due to their robust design (Çolak et al., 2022). Typically, an MLP network consists of three layers. The initial layer, known as the input layer, receives the data utilized for training the neural network. In multilayer networks, data inputted into the system's input layer is forwarded to subsequent layers, and following a series of operations, predictive values are generated in the output layer.

An MLP neural network model has been established to predict the discharging performance of open absorption systems in terms of output air mixing ratio and temperature. Discrepancies between the predicted values from the output layer and the desired target values are computed. To minimize these errors, data is iteratively transmitted from the output layer back to the input layer. This iterative process continues until the desired validation performance is achieved. Following the input layer is the hidden layer, a fundamental component of MLP networks. Each

MLP network model typically includes at least one hidden layer, although in certain instances, multiple hidden layers may be present. The best hyper parameter s chosen to optimize the model and get better result. The "relu" activation function is selected, which allows for non-linear transformations and is suitable for capturing complex patterns in the data. To avoid overfitting, L2 regularization is chosen for regularization in MLPNN. Regularization parameter set to 0.001 to help prevent overfitting by penalizing large parameter values. Hidden layers with 20 neurons are specified, providing the model with the capacity to learn hierarchical representations of the input data. Also, the "adam" solver is utilized, which efficiently optimizes the model's weights during training by dynamically adjusting the learning rate.

3.2 Tree-based Gradient Boosting Regression

Tree-based Gradient Boosting Regressor (GBR) is an ensemble learning technique that builds a predictive model by sequentially combining weak learners, typically decision trees, to minimize a given loss function. GBR has gained widespread popularity due to its ability to handle complex datasets, mitigate overfitting, and deliver superior predictive performance. The concept of boosting originated from Schapire's work (Schapire, 1990). Boosting, in contrast to bagging, generates base models in a sequential manner. It enhances prediction accuracy by progressively creating multiple models, focusing on instances that pose challenges for estimation. During the boosting process, training examples that are difficult to estimate using previous base models are given greater emphasis compared to those that are accurately estimated. Each subsequent base model aims to rectify errors made by its predecessors (Zhang & Haghani, 2015). GBR, compared to RFR, is slower in training due to its sequential nature.

The hyper-parameters for Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR) model are defined as follows: the learning rate is set to 0.2, controlling the step size at each iteration; the maximum depth of each tree (max_depth) is limited to 5, regulating the complexity of the individual trees in the ensemble; the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node (min_samples_split) is set to 2, ensuring a robust splitting process; and finally, the number of boosting stages (n_estimators) is configured to 100, determining the total number of trees in the ensemble. These hyperparameters collectively shape the GBR model's performance and effectiveness in capturing complex relationships within the data while mitigating overfitting.

3.3 Random Forest Regression

Random Forest Regression (RFR) is a versatile machine learning algorithm that belongs to the ensemble learning family. Introduced by Breiman in 2001 (Breiman, 2001), it has gained significant popularity due to its ability to handle complex datasets, mitigate overfitting, and provide robust predictions. In essence, the random forest algorithm builds upon the concept of bagging while ensuring variation within each tree by employing random feature selection. Its theoretical underpinnings also facilitate parallel computing, which can enhance training speed significantly. The predictive accuracy of random forest primarily depends on three key factors: the inter-tree correlation, the effectiveness of individual trees, and the total number of trees in the ensemble (Zhang & Haghani, 2015).

4. Results and discussion

This section shows the evaluation of the test predictions of Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network (MLPNN), Gradient Boosting Regressor (GBR), and Random Forest Regressor (RFR).

In order to evaluate the success of these three algorithms, four different statistical metrics are calculated for all three models. As shown in Table 1 and 2, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is high for all models and ranging from 93%-99%. All the models show a good performance in terms of R-squared in the prediction of air output mixing ratio and temperature. All the statistical metrics indicate high accuracy in forecasting TCF system output air mixing ratio and temperature, with RFR and GBR outperforming MLPNN, respectively. Evaluation metrics, including R-squared, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), highlight the efficacy of the proposed models. Comparing the three mentioned methods' performance in modeling the discharging performance of thermochemical fluid system shows that the random forest models have a higher accuracy in both predicting output air mixing ratio and temperature than the GBR and MLPNN. The evaluation metrics for GBR, RFR, and MLPNN model are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Evaluation metrics of various models test error for output air mixing ratio prediction.

Model	R-squared	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Mean Squared Error (MSE)	Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)
MLPNN	0.928	1.407	4.718	8.51
GBR	0.988	0.56275	0.76659	2.94
RFR	0.9998	0.03428	0.01371	0.241

Table 3: Evaluation metrics of various models test error for output air temperature prediction.

Model	R-squared	Mean absolute error (MAE)	Mean squared error (MSE)	Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)
MLP	0.9772	0.752	1.235	2.62
GBR	0.996	0.25	0.167	0.8422
RFR	0.9997	0.0290	0.01336	0.097

Table 2 and 3 illustrates that the RFR model outperforms both MLP and GBR models in terms of R-squared, MAE, MSE, and MAPE when forecasting both air output mixing ratio and air output temperature. The Random Forest regressor demonstrates remarkable performance, achieving a notable R^2 of 0.999 in predicting both the air output mixing ratio and temperature. Additionally, it yields low MAPE values of 0.241 for air output mixing ratio prediction and 0.097 for temperature prediction. However, MAPE value for mixing ratio and temperature prediction using MLPNN are 8.51 and 2.62, respectively. This superiority is attributed to the RFR model's robustness in handling outliers, whereas MLP and GBR models, being more intricate, are susceptible to overfitting. This suggests that the RFR model may offer more reliable predictions due to its ability to effectively manage outlier data points.

Acknowledging the limitations of the R^2 metric is crucial, for a thorough evaluation of model performance, it's imperative to not solely rely on R^2 values. Instead, a more holistic approach involves supplementing R^2 assessment with thorough residual analysis. By doing so, we gain deeper insights into the model's behavior and its ability to accurately capture the underlying relationships within the data.

a: Residuals for output mixing ratio prediction by MLPNN

b: Actual vs predicted by MLPNN for mixing ratio prediction

c: Residuals for output mixing ratio prediction by GBR

d: Actual vs predicted by GBR for mixing ratio prediction

e: Residuals for output mixing ratio prediction by RFR

f: Actual vs predicted by RFR for mixing ratio prediction

Figure 3: Residual plot for predicting output air mixing ratio by MLP, GBR and RFR (the left side). Actual versus predicted values by MLP, GBR and RFR model for predicting output air mixing ratio (the right side).

The constant variability in residual plot by RFR (Figure 3(e) and Figure 4(e)) shows the estimated parameters are more reliable. In other words, when the spread of predicted values is consistent across the range of observed data, this consistency enhances the robustness of predictions and increases confidence in the model's performance. However, there is more variability in Figure 3(a, and c), and Figure 4(a, and c) which can reject the constant variance assumption. In residual plot for MLP and GBR model, there's almost a pattern like a systematic increase/decrease in the residuals, it suggests that the relationship between the predictors and the target variable is not adequately captured by the model. Also, the residual plot for MLP and GBR does not show a completely randomly scattered points around the horizontal axis.

a: Residuals for output mixing ratio prediction by MLP

b: Actual vs predicted by MLPNN for mixing ratio prediction

c: Residuals for output mixing ratio prediction by GBR

d: Actual vs predicted by GBR for mixing ratio prediction

e: Residuals for output mixing ratio prediction by RFR

f: Actual vs predicted by RFR for mixing ratio prediction

Figure 4: Residual plot for predicting output air temperature by MLP, GBR and RFR (the left side). Actual versus predicted values by MLP, GBR and RFR model for predicting output air mixing ratio (the right side).

The scatter plots of actual versus predicted values are shown in Figure 3(b, d, and f) and Figure 4(b, d, and f) for all three model. This plot provides valuable insights into the performance of the model by visually how well the model's predictions align with the true values. As seen in the Figure 3(b, d, and f) and 4(b, d, and f), the predicted vs actual values have wider dispersion when predicted by MLPNN compared to GBR and RFR. Also, as it is shown the model prediction closely match the actual values in RFR model. The spread of points around the diagonal line can also provide insights into the model's confidence in its predictions. A wider spread of values in MLPNN and GBR indicate higher uncertainty in predictions.

The analysis of graphs reveals that the Random Forest Regression (RFR) model outperforms its counterparts, probably attributed to its robustness in handling outliers.

Therefore, ML models that have been developed specifically RFR have the potential to provide practical uses in real-time monitoring, aiding in the prediction of discharge performance for TCF systems.

The findings demonstrate the potential of machine learning in enhancing reliable prediction of open absorption TCF system performance, contributing to the better planning and decision-making in the application of our system for dehumidification.

5. Conclusion

The utilization of open-absorption thermochemical systems with great hygroscopic potential presents a promising avenue for various applications. However, the conventional approach to analyzing these systems, relying on physics-based models, often entails substantial financial and time investments to carry out experimental studies and determine physical coefficients based on the results.

In this study, a pioneering effort is made to avoid the challenges of model development by employing machine learning techniques. The application of machine learning allows to automate the development of models from the measured data. It has been applied to data acquired in lab in the study. However, given proper parametrization and smart equipment of devices with sensors in operational environment, an ongoing improvement of models by continual learning seems feasible. Specifically, three distinct models—Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Gradient Boosting Regressor (GBR), and Random Forest Regressor (RFR)—are introduced for the prediction of the discharging performance of the thermochemical fluid (TCF) system. Remarkably, our evaluation metrics underscore the superior predictive prowess of the Random Forest Regressor, outperforming both GBR and MLP counterparts in forecasting air output mixing ratio and air temperature. This superiority can be attributed to several factors inherent to RFR. Firstly, its adeptness in handling high-dimensional data renders it particularly suitable for the complex nature of TCF systems. Additionally, RFR exhibits robustness against outliers and mitigates the risk of overfitting, ensuring more reliable predictions. Notably, the computational efficiency of RFR stands out, boasting shorter processing times compared to GBR and MLP models.

Thus, the adoption of Random Forest Regressor enhances prediction accuracy, marking a significant advancement in the analysis of open absorption thermochemical systems. This study sets a precedent for the integration of machine learning methodologies in the optimization and evaluation of similar complex systems, promising further advancements in the field of model development in complex systems.

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7. References

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